

Behaviour of Electrolytic and Metallurgical Copper Electrodes

I. Reduction of Dinitrobenzoic Acid (DNB)

A. A. EL SAMAHY, F. M. EL CHEIKH and S. Z. HENAIN

Chemistry Department, Assiut University, A. R. Egypt

Manuscript received 12 November 1973; accepted 27 August 1974

Dinitrobenzoic acid is reduced both on metallurgical and electrolytic copper cathodes in alkaline and acidic media. The electrolytic copper cathodes are more active towards the reduction of the DNB. The reduction efficiency is higher and potentials of reduction are lower on electrolytic copper cathodes than on metallurgical ones. The DNB is reduced in a step-wise manner both in acidic and alkaline media to give the diamino benzoic acid as the final product.

THE electrolytic reduction of aromatic nitro compounds on all possible electrode materials except on copper has been the subject of many research workers, much more than the electrolytic reduction of aliphatic compounds¹. The only aromatic compound studied on copper and copper amalgam electrodes was methyl *o*-nitrobenzoate in HCl medium².

It is well known that in acidic medium the electroreduction of aromatic nitrocompounds takes place as follows³:

while in alkaline medium the nitroso- and the hydroxylamine formed as intermediates undergo secondary chemical interaction by catalytic condensation to give azo-, azoxy-, and hydrazo-compounds⁴.

It is also known that copper has moderate hydrogen overvoltage which makes it of moderate reducing power, all of which favours the hydroxylamine as the main product⁵.

In the present work metallurgical and electrolytic copper electrodes were used for the reduction of 3-, 5-dinitrobenzoic acid in 1M NaOH and in acidic medium (1M NaOH + 2M CH₃COOH).

Experimental

A. Materials: All chemicals used were reagent grade. Water was doubly distilled. The metallurgical copper electrodes were spiral shaped of 5 cm. length and 1.5 diameter. Electrolytic copper electrodes were made of the same spirals, coated with electrolytic copper (15 nm thickness) deposited from an acid sulphate bath⁶.

B. Efficiency measurements: The diagram (Fig. 1) illustrates the circuit and apparatus used for measurements. The efficiency of reduction was estimated by measuring the total quantity of electricity passed minus that consumed in the hydrogen evolution. The measuring of the quantity of electricity was done by a copper coulometer connected in series with the electrolytic cell.

Fig. 1. The circuit of hydrogen evolution.

C. Polarization measurements: These measurements were carried out galvanostatically by applying a constant current for three minutes and then measuring the electrode potential against a saturated calomel electrode. The current applied was increased gradually after every measurement.

D. Calculation of the order: The calculation of the order of the over-all electrode reaction relative to the depolarizer was carried out by plotting $\log c$ vs. $\log i$ at constant potential

$$\log i = n \log c + K$$

where n is the order, and c is the concentration of the depolarizer.

E. *The energy of activation*: The energies of activation were calculated using the equation suggested by Garbachev⁷,

$$\log i = - \frac{E}{2.303 RT} + \text{constant}$$

where *i* is the current in milliamperes, and *E* is the energy of activation in calories per mole.

Results and Discussion

The polarization curves of cathodic reduction of dinitrobenzoic acid (DNB) in 1*M* NaOH and in acidic solution (Fig. 2 and Fig. 3) show that in both cases the H₂ evolution is the only product in the absence of DNB. The figures also show that the behaviour of the electrolytically deposited Cu cathode (solid lines) is more active in reduction than the metallurgical ones (dotted lines). By increasing the concentration of the substrate the wave heights increase proportionally and the potential range of each wave is the same for all concentrations.

Fig. 2. Cathodic polarization curves during reduction of 3,5 dinitrobenzoic acid in solution of 1*N* NaOH. The concentration of the substrate curve :
 1—0.05*M*
 2—0.0375*M*
 3—0.025*M*
 4—0.0125*M*
 5—0.005*M*
 6—No substrate.
 The dotted lines represent the metallurgical Cu cathode, while the solid lines represent the electrolytic one.

Cathodic Polarization :

In the alkaline medium the H₂ evolution takes place at a relatively higher potential 1.15v (Fig. 2, curve 6). On the addition of DNB strong depolarization takes place with the appearance of three distinguished waves of reduction.

The order (*n*) of the overall electrode reaction relative to DNB calculated from the polarization curves of Fig. 2 was found to be 0.6 below 0.45v and then started suddenly to increase to about 1.0 at

Fig. 3. Cathodic polarization curves during reduction of 3,5 dinitrobenzoic acid in solution of 1*N* NaOH+2.0*N* CH₃COOH. The concentration of the substrate curve :
 1—0.05*M*
 2—0.0375*M*
 3—0.025*M*
 4—0.0125*M*
 5—0.005*M*
 6—No substrate.

0.55v and stayed at this value until 0.7v, where it started suddenly to decrease to 0.6 upto 0.8v, where it remains constant over this potential value.

It can be noticed from the above results that the stability ranges of the order coincide with the potential range of each wave, and the order is the same for the first and the third waves 0.6 but different for the second wave 1.0.

On plotting log *i_d/i_a* - *i* vs *E* for each wave, straight lines were obtained with the following slopes 0.03 for the first and the second waves and 0.062 for the third wave respectively. The slope is equal to 2.303 *RT*/*BZF*, where *Z* is the number of electrons concerned and *B* is a coefficient = 0.5 for cases of comparable diffusion and chemical polarization⁸. Thus, the first and second waves involve 4 electron mechanisms while the third wave is 2 electron transfer step. The same behaviour was noticed for the reduction on electrolytic Cu. This may be due to the reduction of the first nitro group to hydroxylamine in the first wave. The second wave corresponds to the reduction of the second nitro group also to hydroxylamine. The third wave involves the further reduction of one of the hydroxylamines to the amine :

The final reduction of the second hydroxylamine takes place together with the H₂ evolution.

The reduction of DNB in acidic medium takes place at lower potentials than in alkaline medium (Fig. 3). The figure shows the polarization curves where 2 distinctive waves are noticed, the height of which is nearly twice that in the case of the first

and second waves in the alkaline medium. The H₂ evolution takes place at 0.75v vs. S.C.E. Upon the addition of the DNB strong depolarization takes place. The wave height is proportional to the concentration of the substrate (Fig. 3).

The order (*n*) of the overall electrode reaction relative to DNB calculated from the polarization curves of Fig. 3 was found to be 0.6 below 0.35v and then started to increase to 1.0 at 0.45v and remained constant. This is just the same as in the case of the alkaline medium.

The calculation of *Z*, the number of electrons involved in each step of reduction, by the same way as shown for the alkaline medium, confirmed that both first and second waves are 4-electron transfer steps since the slopes of the relation $\log i_a/i_a - i$ against *E* are 0.032 and 0.0313 respectively. This means that the first wave corresponds to the reduction of one of the -NO₂ group to the hydroxylamine, while the second group reduces at the second wave by the same mechanism. Further reduction of the hydroxylamine takes place together with the H₂ evolution.

Reduction Efficiency :

From the experimental data figures 4a and 4b were plotted. In these figures the percent of the total electric current consumed in the reduction is plotted against the current for the different concentrations of the DNB on both the metallurgical and electrolytic Cu. The current efficiency of reduction was found to decrease by increasing the current applied both in acidic and alkaline medium. The higher the concentration of the depolarizer the greater the current efficiency of the reduction. In all cases studied the current efficiency on electrolytic Cu was higher than that on the metallurgical one which indicates that the electrolytic Cu is of higher activity towards the reduction of the DNB. This could be attributed to the fact that the electrodeposited Cu

Fig. 4A. Effect of concentration on the reduction of 3,5 dinitrobenzoic acid in alkaline medium 1N NaOH.

Fig. 4B. Effect of concentration on the reduction of 3,5 dinitrobenzoic acid in acidic medium (1.0N NaOH + 2.0 N CH₃COOH).

possesses more or less oriented crystals with most active surfaces towards the solution side. This makes the reduction of DNB on these active surfaces easier with higher efficiencies at lower reduction potentials (Figs. 4a and 4b). Besides, the actual surface area of the electrolytic Cu may be greater than the apparent one which makes the real current density lower than the calculated one. This fact leads to higher reduction efficiencies at lower electrode potentials.

The Energy of Activation

The calculation of the energy of activation according to equation (1) showed that in alkaline medium the reduction process of DNB always involves higher energies of activation than in acidic media (Table 1). Interestingly enough, the energy of activation calculated for electrolytic Cu cathodes was always lower than those calculated for metallurgical cathodes.

TABLE 1—ENERGY OF ACTIVATION IN ACID ELECTROLYSIS AT DIFFERENT ELECTRODE POTENTIALS

Electrode Potential (in volts)	0.05M (DNB) E Kcal/mole	0.0125M (DNB) E Kcal/mole
0.275	9.5	11.5
0.3	7.42	9.3
0.325	6.10	7.5
0.35	5.05	6.8
0.375	4.79	6.3
0.400	4.78	5.9
0.425		5.8
0.450		5.8
0.500		5.72
0.550		5.70
0.600		5.73

This could also be attributed to the surface properties of the electrolytic Cu as mentioned above.

TABLE 2—ENERGY OF ACTIVATION IN ALKALINE ELECTROLYSIS AT DIFFERENT ELECTRODE POTENTIALS

Electrode Potential (in volts)	0.05M (DNB) E Kcal/mole	0.0125M (DNB) E Kcal/mole
0.375	11.5	13.0
0.400	10.3	11.4
0.425	9.5	9.8
0.450	7.9	8.4
0.475	6.9	7.6
0.500	6.2	7.00
0.525	6.00	6.80
0.550	6.00	6.7
0.600		6.6
0.650		6.6

According to the temperature kinetic theory⁷, if the energy of activation is lower than 7 Kcal/mole and does not change by increasing the potential, then the electrode process is said to be diffusion-controlled, i.e., the diffusion of the reacting species is the rate-determining step. If the energy of activation is higher than Kcal/mole and decreases by increasing the potential, then the electrode reaction is said to be kinetically controlled or the direct

electrochemical step is the rate-determining one. On the other hand, if the energy of activation is higher than 7 Kcal/mole and decreases by increasing the potential until it reaches a constant value below 7 Kcal/mole, the process is said to be kinetically-controlled, changing gradually into a diffusion-controlled one. The last case is noticed in our measurements (see Table 1).

References

1. A. P. TOMILOV, S. G. MAIRONOVSKY, M. YA. FIOSSHIN and V. A. SMIRNOV, "Elektrokhimiya Organicheskikh Soedineniyi," *Khimiya*, 1968.
2. M. YA. FIOSSHIN, K. K. BABIEVSKY and N. A. IZGARISHEV, *D. A. Nauk USSR*, 1955, 104, 744.
3. L. I. ANTROPOV, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1951, 25, 419.
M. LE GUYADER, *Compt. Rend.*, 1962, 254, 4182.
M. LE GUYADER and I. MERCIER, *Compt. Rend.*, 1963, 257, 1307.
4. I. KORSHONOV and A. KIRILLOV, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1948, 18, 785.
L. HOLLEK, *Rev. Polarogr.*, 1963, 11, 129.
5. L. E. TER-MINASYAN, *Izv. A. N. Arm. SSR, Khim. i Khim. Tekhnolog.*, 1957, 10, 173.
6. "MODERN ELECTROPLATING". The Electrochemical Society, 1963, p. 154.
7. S. V. GARBACHEV and Y. N. YOURKEVICH, *Zh. Fiz. Khim.*, 1954, 28, 1120.
8. S. YA. POPOV, *Tr. Novocherikasky Institute, Elektrokhimiya*, 1959, 179, 105.